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Relationship between Body Weights, Body Conformation Score (BCS), FAMACHA, Fecal Egg Count (FEC), and Packed Cell Volume (PCV) in Kiko Meat Goats in spring, summer, Fall and Winter.

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Abstract

In Alabama, the Kiko meat goat (developed and imported from New Zealand) is the most widespread and well-known breed constituting about 70% of the total goat population in the state. This study was carried out to evaluate the seasonal (winter, spring, summer and fall) relationships between body weight (BWT), body conformation scores (BCS), FAMACHA, fecal egg count (FEC) and packed cell volume (PCV) of Kiko-meat goats managed under semi-intensive production system in southeast Alabama. Mature Kiko meat goats (n = 15; age = 9-12 months) were utilized. BWT was recorded using a standard scale, while BCS was assessed by subjective scores (ranging from 1= emaciated to 5= obese). FEC was obtained from fecal materials using the McMaster slide. The observation of the conjunctiva of the ventral eyelid for paleness, was as quantified as a FAMACHA score. FAMACHA scores showed moderate seasonal correlations with BCS (r = -0.53), low negative correlation with PCV (r = -0.20). Body weight showed a high strong relationship with BCS (r = 80). The present study provides evidence for the possible use of FAMACHA© as a tool to identify and select Kiko meat goats that need anthelmintic treatment against parasitic worms as has been shown in other small ruminants. Results also suggests that Kiko meat goats that scored 1, 2 or 3 with the FAMACHA© chart can be considered non-anemic and not in need of deworming, while those in categories 4 and 5 are in need of deworming

Keywords: FAMACHA, PCV, Fecal Egg Count, Kiko Meat Goats, Seasons

Introduction

Goats are important for both commercial and subsistent farming systems in rural southeastern United States. Limited resource producers keep goats primarily for meat, milk and as a source of income since most subsistent farmers cannot afford to keep cattle. They are very versatile because not only do they provide goods but they also provide services such as vegetation management by eating unwanted vegetation in fields, and they can also prevent fuel fires by reducing fuel load (Solaiman, 2007). The tremendous changes in demand that are ongoing within the goat community in the course of the last two decades has created the opportunity for goat production to become widespread (Hart, 2001). However, given the substantial increase in the U.S. chevon imports in recent years, there appears to be continued room for growth in the U.S. meat-goat industry (Sande *et al.*, 2005).

In Alabama, goats of any breed or crossbreed are eventually slaughtered for human consumption (Thompson, 2006). With the exception of the South African Boer and Kiko goats there are no true meat goat breeds in the United States. However, there are few breeds that stand out as more specialized for meat production. These are the Spanish, Myotonic (Tennessee Fainting Goat), Nubian and Pygmy goats. In Alabama, the Kiko meat goat (developed and imported from New Zealand) is the most widespread and well-known breed constituting about 70% of the total goat population in the state. Through a series of the cross breeding of feral

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does and an assortment of different breeds of dairy bucks, the ultimate development of the Kiko goat breed came into existence (Pellerin and Browning, 2012). The Boer goat encompasses the meatiness as well as growth that both consumers and producers demand and want. However, in recent times many Boer goats are more sought after as show goats thus providing less emphasis on traits that are essential to produce commercially viable meat goats. The Kiko goat, however, has been gaining traction in popularity amongst meat goat producers. In recent years research was conducted at Tennessee State University that showed Kiko goats to be one of the most profitable and productive breeds in a study where multiple breeds were compared (Murphy, 2016).

The growth of the meat goat industry in the southeastern United States is being increasingly hampered by the increasingly difficult problem of controlling anthelmintic-resistant gastrointestinal nematodes (GIN). The species of primary concern is *Haemonchus contortus*, a highly pathogenic blood-feeder that causes anemia and reduced productivity and can lead to death in heavily infected animals (Burke et al., 2007). Gastrointestinal parasites are a major problem for small-scale Alabama meat goat farmers and can lead to economic and production losses (Solaiman, 2007). Southeast Alabama is hot and humid in summer and fall months, which favors high prevalence of internal parasites and diseases. However, the Southeastern region appears to be more favorable for Kiko goats' production due to their increased parasitic resistance and lower incidence of hoof problems. Wade (2004). Reported that the Kiko meat goat demonstrates a higher level of parasitic resistance

Control of gastrointestinal nematode (GIN) populations is becoming a difficult task in many countries around the world due to the widespread existence of worm populations with resistance against two or more anthelmintic (AH) classes (Torres-Acosta et al., 2012). As the situation of AH resistance worsens, it is necessary to seek for new management practices to delay further development of resistant GIN isolates.

The major limitation to instituting a selective parasite treatment approach has been the lack of an efficient and practicable means of identifying those animals requiring deworming or treatment. This problem can be solved by monitoring a seasonal variation of fecal egg count (FEC), and FAMACHA© scores of Kiko goat herds in southeast Alabama as was done in Nigeria (Nwosu et al., 2007). FAMACHA scoring identifies anemia in small ruminants, the main symptom of barber's pole worm infestation. Dr. Faffa Malan developed a five color FAMACHA scoring chart that corresponds to a sheep or goat's bottom eyelid color. Pale pink to white indicates anemia; the animal should be dewormed (Jan van Wyk and Gareth, 2002).

FAMACHA scores were developed using ranges of PCV (Malan et al., 2001; Vatta et al., 2001; Kaplan et al., 2004), such that there is an inverse relationship between these indices. Sheep or goats are considered to be anemic when PCV falls below 19%, and FAMACHA scores of 3 or greater are an indicator of anemia (Kaplan et al., 2004). However, a number of conditions can produce anemia, and the potential value of FAMACHA scores as an indicator of gastrointestinal nematode resistance relies on the assumption that observed anemia is primarily caused by blood loss arising from infection with *H. contortus*. Because *H. contortus* was not always the predominant nematode, as indicated by culture of worm eggs from some locations, FAMACHA score would not necessarily always reflect changes in FEC (Notter et al., 2017). However, when *H. contortus* is prevalent, FAMACHA scores reflect joint effect of resistance to gastrointestinal nematodes (i.e., the ability to avoid infection and expel larvae and adult nematodes from the gut) and resilience to infection (i.e., the ability to maintain normal levels of PCV despite the presence of adult nematodes in the gut).

Another common diagnostic method to assess the size and significance of worm burdens is to count the eggs shed by these worms in feces or excreta. This is called a fecal egg count (FEC) or worm egg count (WEC). The most common and efficient way to obtain fecal egg counts for sheep, goats, young cattle and horses is to use the Modified McMaster Test. This is a flotation test that separates parasite eggs from debris based on density; the eggs float to the surface of the counting chamber

There is still difficulty in the accurate diagnosis of haemonchosis as a specific disease entity both by veterinarians, veterinary assistants and farmers. By the time typical clinical signs such as "bottle jaw",

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emaciation and weakness are noticed, the disease would have reached an advanced stage with poor prognosis. Hence, the need for a simplified and accurate system for the diagnosis of the disease entity in goat populations in Alabama. In addition, other factors such as nutrition, ectoparasitic infections, and extant diseases may influence the anemic state of the animal. It has been recommended (Spicket, 2009) that the FAMACHA© system be supported by other criteria such as clinical signs and weight loss, body condition score and fecal egg count.

Body Condition Score (BCS) is. BCS is the best simple indicator of body fat reserves which can be used by the animal itself in the periods of high energy demands, various stresses or under nutrition condition, and thus widely accepted indicator of post nutritional status (Caldeira and Portugal, 2007). The technique can be used for various species of animal like cattle, sheep and goat as well. BCS is used for evaluating the adequacy of previous feed supply, determining the future feed requirements, assessing the health status of individual animals, establishing the condition of animals during routine animal management and welfare inspections (Maurya et al., 2008) and in meat production systems (Suiter, 1994). On the farm, body weight or heart girth is usually monitored to quantify status of animal, but these techniques have a number of disadvantages. First, weight scales are cumbersome, Second, weight per se does not reflect an animal's condition

The body weight of the goat generally has two components, the basic skeletal size and the degree of fatness (body condition) of the animal. Due to the variation in skeletal size between does, body weight alone cannot indicate the degree of fatness. BCS is thus an estimation of muscle and fat development of an animal and is correlated with the direct measurement of back fat depth or the proportion of fat in the animal body – providing a better estimate than body weight alone (Russel et al., 1969).

The primary objective of the present project was to investigate seasonal (winter, spring, summer and fall) variations FAMACHA scores and fecal egg count (FEC) of Kiko-meat goats managed under semi-intensive production system in at Caprine Research and Education Unit, Tuskegee University, Tuskegee, Alabama. Secondary objective is to evaluate the FAMACHA© chart system in relation to FEC, PCV, BCS and BWT so as to ascertain its accuracy as a tool for detection of clinical anemia due *H. contortus* in Kiko meat goats.

Materials & methods

Goat Management

This study was conducted at the Caprine Research and Education Unit of the George Washington Carver Agricultural Experiment Station at Tuskegee University, Tuskegee, Alabama (32.43N, 85.71W). Tuskegee is located in the southeastern region of the United States, sits 183 meters above sea level, and has an annual precipitation amount of 1222mm. The Tuskegee University Animal Care and Use Committee approved the herd management protocol used in this project.

For this project a total number of 15 Kiko goats that were semi-intensively managed in Summer, Fall, Winter, and Spring were utilized. Goats were between the ages of 1 and 2 years old and were dewormed three times during the research period. All animals were managed on tall fescue (*Festuca arundinacea*) and Bermuda grass (*Cynodondactylon*) pastures and supplemented with Bermuda grass hay (*Cynodondactylon*) for ad libitum consumption. Animals were also supplemented with 341 g/d of alfalfa (17% crude protein, 1.5% crude fat, 30% crude fiber) and corn (7% crude protein, 3% crude fat, 4% crude fiber), and had access to trace mineral salt blocks. All research animals had access to water daily.

Blood samples were collected with an 18-gauge needle by jugular venipuncture between 8:00AM and 10:00AM once a week for three weeks for each of the calendar seasons, Summer, Fall, Winter and Spring. During each collection period atmospheric temperature, humidity and rainfall were also recorded.

Packed Cell Volume

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Microhematocrit tubes were filled 3 quarters of the way with blood and the bottom of the hematocrit tubes were packed with clay and were then placed in a microhematocrit centrifuge for 5 minutes. Samples were removed and placed on a hematocrit card reader which reads from 0% to 100% which may be used to assess anemia. The lower the percentage reported indicates the severity of anemia.

Body Weight and Body Condition Score.

Body weight was recorded using a digital scale. Body condition scoring was subjectively determined using palpable body condition scoring scale 1 to 5, (1 being emaciated and 5 being obese). Both Body weight and condition scores were taken each time blood collections occurred for consistent values.

FAMACHA

FAMACHA was also recorded. FAMACHA record keeping was scored using a FAMACHA card scale of 1 to 5. One indicates optimal, while five represents highly anemic. FAMACHA is assessed while looking at the animal's mucous membrane of the eye.

Fecal Egg Counting

Fecal egg testing was conducted at the last two weeks of each blood collection using the McMaster technique (Whitlock,1948) to identify *Haemonchus contortus* which are approximately 70-85 μm in size. Two grams of fecal matter was weighed, and 28 milliliters of fecal flotation solution (with a specific gravity of (1.18-1.20) were weighed out. The fecal flotation solution and fecal sample were mixed well and were allowed to stand for five to ten minutes. After five to ten minutes the solution was then strained, and the solution was then filled in the McMaster slide. The solution was allowed to sit for at least five minutes. The samples must be read within sixty minutes after this step. The next process included counting the eggs on a light microscope. In order to count the eggs, first, focus the grid lines of the McMaster slide using the 4x lens using the focus knob and make further adjustments. The next process was to proceed to the 10x lens and focus the grid on the grid lines of the McMaster slide. Accordingly, the next step was to locate the corner of one grid and move up and down through the lanes counting the eggs. The last step was to count both grids and calculate the number of eggs per gram.

Environmental Conditions

Seasonal conditions (temperature, rainfall and relative humidity) were monitored and recorded as shown in Table 1.

Statistical Analysis

All results are expressed as \pm standard deviation (SD). SAS 2006 $\text{\textcircled{R}}$ statistical software calculated the minimum and maximum values to determine the range, mean, and standard deviation of the mean. The effects of season on FAMACHA, FEC, BWT and BCS profiles of goats was analyzed by an analysis of variance (ANOVA) using SAS 2012 $\text{\textcircled{R}}$ statistical software. Pearson's correlation method was used to determine the degree of relationship between PCV, FEC, BWT, BCS and FAMACHA $\text{\textcircled{C}}$, scores)

Results and Discussion

Means and standard deviation values for all variables recorded in the Spring, Summer, Fall, and Winter months are presented in Table 2. Results include a mean of 59.9 kg \pm 11.7 kg for body weight in the spring, 46.2 kg \pm 11.4 kg in summer, 46.3 kg \pm 13.6 kg, in the fall, and 46.5 kg \pm 10.1 kg in the winter respectively.

For body condition scores, results show 3.0 \pm 0.0 in the spring, 2.7 \pm 0.4 in the summer, 2.6 \pm 0.5 in the fall, and 2.6 \pm 0.5 in the winter respectively. Fecal egg counts values were 210.3 \pm 174.08 in the spring, 315.5 \pm

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263.9 in the summer, 525.5 ± 327.6 in the fall, and 395.0 ± 292.9 in the winter respectively. For packed cell volume % values include 29.7 ± 1.4 , in the spring, 27.7 ± 4.4 in the summer, 27.7 ± 3.3 in the fall, and 30.2 ± 4.2 in the winter respectively. Further values include 3.0 ± 0.0 for FAMACHA in the spring, 3.8 ± 0.4 in the summer, 4.0 ± 0.0 in the fall, and of 3.4 ± 0.5 in the winter respectively.

As shown in Table 3, recorded body weights were highly significantly influenced by season ($P \leq 0.01$). Body condition scores showed significant seasonal differences ($P \leq 0.05$). Fecal egg counts showed no significant seasonal variations ($P \geq 0.05$). Also, packed cell volume % values were not significantly influenced by seasons ($P \geq 0.05$). However, FAMACHA scores were showed highly significant seasonal variations ($P \leq 0.01$).

Values obtained representing body condition score are based upon a subjective analysis utilizing a scoring card to determine overall body conformation. Locations in Europe and Great Britain utilize score cards based on subjective assessments of the level of fat as well as muscle thickness in relation to the backbone (Treacher et al., 1986).

Table 4 displays the correlation coefficients for PCV, BCS, FEC, BWT and FAMACHA scores. FAMACHA scores showed a significant low negative relationship with packed cell volume, which represents the red blood cells ($r = -0.20$). Body weight and body condition score showed strong and positive relationship ($r = 0.80$). Body condition scoring refers to the fleshiness of a goat, and the most ideal areas to assess body condition score (BCS) include over the ribs, the backbone, and the side of the spine on either side (Spahr, 2004). FEC and PCV showed a low correlation coefficient ($r = 0.15$). In addition, FAMACHA and body condition score had a to moderate correlation ($r = -0.53$). Karki et al., (2020) reported similar correlations values between body condition score and FAMACHA with (r) ranging from -0.18 to -0.64 . Also, body condition score showed a negative correlation with fecal egg count ($P < 0.001$, $r = -0.38$).

The FAMACHA scoring system has been recommended as an on-farm strategy to monitor anemia and, by implication, parasite loads in sheep and goats (Kaplan et al., 2004; Burke et al., 2007). Scores of 1 through 5 are assigned by comparing the color of animals' ocular mucous membranes to a color chart (Malan et al., 2001; Van Wyk and Bath, 2002). Under summer grazing conditions, the most likely cause of anemia in sheep and goat flocks in the USA is parasitism by *Haemonchus contortus*, a blood-sucking abomasal nematode (Kaplan et al., 2004), and FAMACHA scoring has been recommended to allow identification and strategic deworming of animals with clinical infections with *H. contortus*. Strategic deworming of only symptomatic individuals can prevent or delay development of drug resistance in the worm population (van Wyk, 2001)

Since FAMACHA scores were developed based on blood packed cell volume (PCV; Malan et al., 2001; Vatta et al., 2001), a relatively strong relationship between these variables has been demonstrated in sheep and goats (Kaplan et al., 2004; Burke et al., 2007; Sotomaier et al., 2012). Riley and Van Wyk (2009) also reported heritable genetic variation in FAMACHA scores and postulated that selection for low scores could improve resistance and/or resilience to infection with *H. contortus*. However, associations between FAMACHA scores and fecal egg counts (FEC) were often (Kaplan et al., 2004), though not always (Burke et al., 2007), less strong than those between FAMACHA scores and PCV. Fecal egg counts are generally considered to be the most effective measure of parasite resistance in live animals, and use of FAMACHA scores to improve resistance to *H. contortus* would require a substantial association between FAMACHA scores and FEC.

Selection for resistance, or for a combination of resistance and resilience, has advantages over selection for only resilience because animals that are resilient, but not resistant, continue to shed nematode eggs, contaminating pastures and increasing the opportunity for infection in nonresistant individuals and younger animals that have not yet developed resistance (Bishop, 2012). In particular, crossbred lambs produced by susceptible sire breeds face greater infection pressures if their dams are resilient to infection, but can be protected from infection by resistant dams.

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The value of FAMACHA scores for genetic improvement of gastrointestinal nematode resistance thus relies on a direct association between FAMACHA scores and FEC. This is best determined at a time of first exposure to *H. contortus*, typically between 90 and 120 d of age (Notter et al., 2017).

Fecal egg counts have been used as a predictor of breeding values for parasite resistance in industry programs in Australia and the U.S.A. (Notter, 2013; Brown and Fogarty, 2017), usually after application of logarithmic or cube-root transformation. Interest exists in using FAMACHA scores as an alternative or supplement to FEC measurements in prediction of breeding values for parasite resistance. Use of FAMACHA scores as an alternative to FEC would avoid the need for fecal collections and the expense of laboratory determination of FEC. FAMACHA scores were shown to be heritable in South African Merino sheep (Riley and Van Wyk, 2009), but the limited range in FAMACHA scores in most flocks would potentially also limit variation in resulting estimated breeding value. Use of FAMACHA scores to predict FEC would, however, be useful in flocks that practice selective deworming based on FAMACHA scores. In such flocks, selective deworming of highly parasitized lamb or kids may invalidate later measurements of FEC in these lambs and kids.

Although producers can benefit from reduced anthelmintic costs by using the FAMACHA system, the most significant benefit is in its ability as a tool to maintain a population of *H. contortus* in refugia. Anthelmintic resistance will develop slowly if the number of *H. contortus* that are not exposed to anthelmintic and maintained in refugia is high. In the current study, had eye scores of ≤ 3 been used for making treatment decisions, 65% of sheep and 61% of goats would have remained untreated. With these untreated animals, sufficiently large refugia should be maintained that is expected to greatly reduce the rate with which anthelmintic resistance will develop. Although producers can benefit from reduced anthelmintic costs by using the FAMACHA system, the most significant benefit is in its ability as a tool to maintain a population of *H. contortus* in refugia. Anthelmintic resistance will develop slowly if the number of *H. contortus* that are not exposed to anthelmintic and maintained in refugia is high. In the current study, had eye scores of ≤ 3 been used for making treatment decisions, 65% of sheep and 61% of goats would have remained untreated. With these untreated animals, sufficiently large refugia should be maintained that is expected to greatly reduce the rate with which anthelmintic resistance will develop. Although producers can benefit from reduced anthelmintic costs by using the FAMACHA system, the most significant benefit is in its ability as a tool to maintain a population of *H. contortus* in refugia. Anthelmintic resistance will develop slowly if the number of *H. contortus* that are not exposed to anthelmintic and maintained in refugia is high. In the current study, had eye scores of ≤ 3 been used for making treatment decisions, 65% of sheep and 61% of goats would have remained untreated. With these untreated animals, sufficiently large refugia should be maintained that is expected to greatly reduce the rate with which anthelmintic resistance will develop.

Producers can benefit from reduced anthelmintic costs by using the FAMACHA system, the most significant benefit is in its ability as a tool to maintain a population of *H. contortus* in refugia. Anthelmintic resistance will develop slowly if the number of *H. contortus* that are not exposed to anthelmintic and maintained in refugia is high. a good indicator of infection with *H. contortus*. small regression values in this study indicate that there were many other factors that contributed to changes in BCS. Because haemonchosis can develop so rapidly, a reduction in body condition or body weight will likely not be apparent during an acute infection. Others have found no relationship between BCS and FEC (Vatta et al., 2002), nor body weight and worm counts (Roberts and Swan, 1982) when *H. contortus* was the pre-dominant nematode. Noting changes in BCS may be

Although there was a significant relationship between BCS and PCV or FEC, BCS by itself is not a good indicator of infection with *H. contortus*. The small correlation values in this study indicate that there were many other factors that contributed to changes in BCS. Because haemonchosis can develop so rapidly, a reduction in body condition or body weight will likely not be apparent during an acute infection. Others have found no relationship between BCS and FEC (Vatta et al., 2002), nor body weight and worm counts (Roberts and Swan, 1982) when *H. contortus* was the pre- dominant nematode.

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The FAMACHA system has proven to be a valuable tool that producers can use to identify animals in need of treatment, to reduce the number of animals to be treated, thereby saving dewormer and contributing to more worms in refugia. Because worms are over-dispersed among animals in a herd/flock, a relatively small number of animals are infected with most of the worms (Barger, 1985; Hoste et al., 2001).

Furthermore, within a herd/flock it tends to be the same animals that are consistently infected with high worm burdens over time. Using the FAMACHA system, animals that repeatedly require treatment can be identified and culled to reduce the herd/flock worm load. In addition, selection of resilient (the ability to withstand worm infection) animals occurs by using FAMACHA.

Some animals may harbor worms with-out becoming anemic, but typically susceptible animals with a high number of worms become anemic. Genetic progress can be made toward selection of a more resilient group of animals (Bisset and Morris,1996; Bisset et al., 2001). The FAMACHA systems should continue to be used in consultation with technical assistance to develop individualized internal parasite control programs. Also, FAMACHA scores have potential to improve breeding value estimates in programs designed to genetically improve parasite resistance.

Conclusions

The objective of this study was to evaluate the relationship between FEC, PCV, FAMACHA score, BCS and BWT of Kiko meat goats to determine performance differences associated with indicators of GIN parasites. The FEC could potentially have negative implications in flocks with elevated GIN parasite loads and poor nutrition, but the weight loss for average GIN parasite loads was minimal in this study. Although FEC is an objective indicator of GIN parasites, selecting for reduced FEC may not significantly change the growth in moderately challenged animals. Goats that did not require treatment were likely more profitable given the treatment cost and better weight gain. As such, it is beneficial to select for animals that do not require treatment for GIN parasites and subsequently would be less prone to reduced weight gain. Results with FAMACHA scores were most dramatic for more extreme cases of anemia, but no body weight or body condition score differences existed between scores of 1 and 2 as expected.

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Authors Contributions:

Dr. Chukwuemeka Okere, Coordinator, Animal & Veterinary Sciences Program, Tuskegee University supervised K. Lane who carried out parts of this work in partial fulfillment for the degree of M.Sc. in animal & Veterinary Sciences.

K. Lane – M.Sc. Graduate Student (Completed).

Dr. Nar Gurung - Research-Extension Professor and Director of Caprine Research and Education Unit, College of Agriculture, Environment and Nutrition Sciences. Tuskegee University, was responsible for animal management.

Conflict of Interest:

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this article.

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Table 1. Seasonal Variations in Environmental Conditions.

Item	Season	Mean	SD	Minimum	Maximum
Temperature Collection °C	Spring	13.3	2.55	11.1	16.1
	Summer	23.6	2.50	21.1	26.1
	Fall	13.8	8.61	8.88	23.8
	Winter	6.08	11.2	-2.7	18.8
High °C	Spring	25.7	3.59	21.6	28.3
	Summer	32.9	1.15	31.6	33.8
	Fall	23.6	1.27	22.2	24.4
	Winter	16.07	7.85	7.22	22.2
Low °C	Spring	10.1	0.28	10.0	10.5
	Summer	21.1	1.61	19.4	22.2
	Fall	6.47	2.31	3.88	8.33
	Winter	4.98	10.5	-3.88	16.6
Humidity%	Spring	71.6	18.1	55.0	91.0
	Summer	83.3	7.63	75.0	90.0
	Fall	88.0	8.0	80.0	96.0
	Winter	82.0	21.6	57.0	95.0
Rainfall cm	Spring	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Summer	0.02	0.04	0.00	0.07
	Fall	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Winter	0.87	1.51	0.00	2.61

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Table 2. Descriptive Statistics for Body Conformation Scores, FAMACHA, FEC, and PCV in Kiko Meat Goats

Trait	Season	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Body Weight, kg (BWT)	Spring	59.9	11.7	43.5	80.0
	Summer	46.2	11.4	29.0	62.0
	Fall	46.3	13.6	27.0	65.5
	Winter	46.5	10.1	33.5	62.0
Body Condition Scores (1 – 5) (BCS)	Spring	3.0	0.0	3.0	3.0
	Summer	2.7	0.4	2.0	3.0
	Fall	2.6	0.5	2.0	3.0
	Winter	2.6	0.5	2.0	3.0
Fecal Egg Counting/g	Spring	210.3	174.08	1.0	500.0
	Summer	315.5	263.9	1.0	750.0
	Fall	525.5	327.6	2.0	1000.0
	Winter	395.0	292.9	100.0	900.0
PCV%	Spring	29.7	1.4	28.0	32.0
	Summer	27.7	4.4	20.0	34.0
	Fall	27.7	3.3	20.0	32.0
	Winter	30.2	4.2	26.0	42.0
FAMACHA (1-5)	Spring	3.0	0.0	3.0	3.0
	Summer	3.8	0.4	3.0	4.0
	Fall	4.0	0.0	4.0	4.0
	Winter	3.4	0.5	3.0	4.0

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Table 3. Seasonal Differences in Body Conformation Scores, FAMACHA, FEC, and PCV in Kiko Meat Goats (P-Values)

TRAIT	SEASON				P-values	Significance
	SPRING	SUMMER	FALL	WINTER		
Body Weight, kg (BWT)	59.9 ± 11.7	46.2 ± 11.4	46.3 ± 13.6	46.5 ± 10.1	0.004	**
Body Condition Scores (1 – 5) (BCS)	3.0 ± 0.0	2.7 ± 0.4	2.6 ± 0.5	2.6 ± 0.5	0.0405	*
Fecal Egg Counting/g	210.3±174.08	315.5±263.9	525.5±327.6	395.0±292.9	0.08	NS
Packed Cell Volume PCV%	29.7 ± 1.4	27.7 ± 4.4	27.7 ± 3.3	30.2 ± 4.2	0.11	NS
FAMACHA (1-5)	3.3 ± 0.0	3.8 ± 0.4	4.0 ± 0.0	3.4 ± 0.5	0.001	**

*Significant if $P \leq 0.05$

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Table 4. Phenotypic Correlations Coefficient (*r*) between Body Conformation, Body Weight, FAMACHA, Fecal Egg Count and Packed Cell Volume in Kiko Meat Goats

Parameter	<i>r</i>
Body Weight vs. Body Condition Score	0.80
FAMACHA vs. Body Condition Score	-0.53
Fecal Egg Count vs. Body Condition Score	-0.08
Packed Cell Volume vs. Body Condition Score	0.30
FAMACHA vs. Body Weight	-0.50
Fecal Egg Count vs. Body Weight	0.08
Packed Cell Volume vs. Body Weight	0.20
FAMACHA vs. Fecal Egg Count	0.26
FAMACHA vs. Packed Cell Volume	-0.20
Fecal Egg Count vs. Packed Cell Volume	0.15